

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Laying hen

Level: Husbandry

Keywords: Behaviour, Enrichment, Housing system

Question raised by the requestor

Is the extra front and backspace of the nest usable for the laying hens to lay the eggs, or when measuring the dimension of the nest do we simply consider the dimension of the mat?

Answer

Introduction

Pre-lay and nesting behaviours are among the highest motivated behaviours in laying hens, and both are behavioural needs (Weeks and Nicol, 2006; Hemsworth and Edwards, 2020; EFSA, 2023). During pre-laying behaviour, hens search for a suitable nest site and perform nest building behaviour. Pre-laying behaviour is followed by laying an egg (oviposition). Afterwards, hens stay in the nest for a period while resting (Cooper and Appleby, 1996; Cooper and Appleby, 2003; EFSA, 2023).

Nest attractiveness, social facilitation and internal biological rhythm (hens mainly lay eggs during the morning hours) may result in overcrowding, even smothering, if nests are not provided in sufficient quantities to allow synchronous nesting by all hens (Villanueva et al. 2017). In addition, insufficient nest space may result in hens performing pre-lay behaviour and oviposition in the litter, resulting in floor eggs. Hence, nest designs should be appropriate (in quantity, quality and size) to allow hens to perform pre-lay behaviours and oviposition with minimal competition to avoid frustration, stress and possibly retained eggs (Villanueva et al., 2017).

EFSA opinion listed characteristics needed for hens' nest (EFSA, 2023):

- **Nest floor:** Hens prefer a soft nest floor substrate which they can mould with their body and feet and which allows nest-building behaviour (Duncan and Kite, 1989), such as straw, which is more suitable than plastic floor, synthetic grass or wire mesh (Huber et al., 1985; Struelens et al., 2005; Struelens et al., 2008).
- **Size:** Hens are known to prefer smaller group nests (e.g., 0.43 m²) compared with larger ones (e.g., 0.86 m²) (Ringgenberg et al., 2014). The use of central partitions improves the attractiveness of group nests (Ringgenberg et al., 2015). According to EFSA (2023), there is no scientific evidence to question what is applied in farms in the EU, namely at least 1 nest for every 7 hens and for group nests at least 1 m² of nest space for a maximum of 120 hens.
- **Enclosure:** Hens prefer enclosed nests (i.e., covered from both sides, the back and the top; Appleby and McRae, 1986). Group nests are more likely to be used when they have a non-transparent front curtain, and the other three sides are enclosed. The hens value the protection by the more closed front of the one-piece curtain, but the sliced curtains provide an easier access for nest inspections by the hens (Stämpfli et al., 2013).
- **Slope:** The floor of nests is sloping, thereby allowing the eggs to roll away to the egg belt without breaking. When comparing with 18% slope, 12% is preferred by hens (Stämpfli et al., 2011). A slope of 14% is currently practised in the EU.

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Area of the "step rail" proposed in concerned aviaries

The area above the step rail in nests can be used for the hens as an extra space to accommodate the head (Figures 1A and 1B), but not its feet. The nest space is only usable when the hen can stand and walk on it. The hen cannot move or lay on/in the space above the step rail. In addition, it is not considered in the list of adequate characteristics of a hen nest described in the introduction as it is not a part of the nest (from the floor to the top). Furthermore, as the floor ends with the mat, this "step rail" area does not meet the preference of laying hens for a soft nest floor substrate that they can mould.

Figure 1: A) detail of the step rail at the end of the nest (side view) B) modified drawing to understand how the hen can interact with the available space.

Extra-front area

The described nest has a part at the entrance of solid metal flooring, before the nest mat, but after the nest curtains (Figure 2). This extra-front area does not meet the preference of laying hens for a soft nest floor substrate that they can mould. Therefore, the "extra-front" is unlikely to be perceived by the laying hens as suitable nest area.

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Figure 2: The red circle highlights the front space (solid metal flooring) between the curtains (1) and the nest mat (3); (2) indicates the step rail (side view).

Conclusions

Based on the current scientific knowledge of the preferences and behavioural needs of laying hens, only the enclosed nest area with a mat that allows moulding behaviour is likely to be considered by the hens as usable nest area. This excludes the “step rail” and the “extra front”.

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